

On the Stress Wave Velocity of Fiber Reinforced Rectangular Bar by Means of Finite Prism Method

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ABSTRACT

The phase and group velocities of the stress wave propagating in the rectangular bar which is reinforced by the fibers oriented in rectangular array over the cross section, are solved by means of the "Finite Integration Transforms".

The dynamic finite prism method is in use, on the assumption that the fiber carries concentrated mass and stiffness and reacts as "Timoshenko beam" in the transverse direction.

The dispersion characteristics of wave velocity with wave number which is effected by the orientation of the fibers as well as the shape of the cross section, are numerically illustrated in the figures.

INTRODUCTION

It is known that the stress wave which propagates in the rectangular bar, disperses on account of its finite length of the cross section. On the other hand the equi-spacing fibers reinforcing the matrix also cause the stress wave dispersion on another account.

The aim of this paper is to find how these effects appear on the harmonic stress wave travelling in the fiber reinforced rectangular bar.

Fraser⁽¹⁾, Nigro⁽²⁾, Tanaka et al.⁽³⁾ investigated the stress wave propagation in the homogeneous isotropic rectangular bar and presented the dispersion properties due to the size of the cross section.

Achenbach et al.⁽⁴⁾ and Hegemier et al.⁽⁵⁾ studied on the stress wave propagation in the infinite fiber reinforced composite and concluded the interval of the fiber caused the dispersion of the wave.

The customary approach mostly consists in replacing the composite by a homogeneous medium whose material constants are determined in terms of the material constants and the geometry of each constituent of the composite⁽⁶⁾.

In this paper the dynamic finite prism method is in use, on the assumption that the fiber carries concentrated mass and stiffness and reacts as "Timoshenko beam" in the transverse directions.

Thus obtained equations lead to an eigenvalue matrix for phase velocity, by means of "Finite Integration Transform" ⁽⁷⁾.

The dispersion characteristics of phase velocity of harmonic stress wave with wave number are numerically obtained, making use of iteration method for eigenvalue matrix of phase velocity, and effects of elastic modulus ratio between fiber

and matrix E_f/E and aspect ratio of the cross section b/a on its characteristics are shown in the figures.

THEORY

As described before, the fibers are in rectangular array over the cross section, and each array may represent a prism element which is supposed to have linear displacement distributions over the cross section.

Multiplying the dynamic equations of equilibrium of forces with the weight functions and integrating them over all volume with the boundary conditions on the crosswise surfaces, we have

$$\int_V L_1 \left(\frac{\partial \sigma_x}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \tau_{xy}}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial \tau_{xz}}{\partial z} - \rho \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial t^2} \right) dV = 0,$$

$$\int_V L_2 \left(\frac{\partial \tau_{xy}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \sigma_y}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial \tau_{yz}}{\partial z} - \rho \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial t^2} \right) dV = 0,$$

$$\int_V L_3 \left(\frac{\partial \tau_{xz}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \tau_{yz}}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial \sigma_z}{\partial z} - \rho \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial t^2} \right) dV = 0$$
(1)

where

$$L_1 = \cos \frac{m\pi}{\ell} x f_1(y) g_1(z),$$

$$L_2 = \sin \frac{m\pi}{\ell} x f_2(y) g_2(z),$$

$$L_3 = \sin \frac{m\pi}{\ell} x f_3(y) g_3(z),$$

V = total volume, ℓ = length of bar,

ρ = density of material,

we obtain a matrix expression between the nodal forces and the nodal displacement with respect to the prism element.

Again taking the equilibrium of forces at the node, involving the three components of mass force, the axial force of the fibers and its transversal force based on Timoshenko beam action, we finally get the expression as follows:

$$([K] - \frac{\partial}{\partial t^2} [M]) \{U\} = 0 \quad (2)$$

where $[K]$ is a symmetrical matrix of size 5×5 and the elements of the matrix are as follows:

$$k_{11} = \frac{2\mu + \lambda}{36} \bar{\Delta}_y \bar{\Delta}_z^2 D_x^2 + \frac{\mu}{6\lambda_2^2} \bar{\Delta}_y \bar{\Delta}_z^2 D_x^2 + \frac{\mu}{6\lambda_2^2} \bar{\Delta}_y^2 \bar{\Delta}_z^2 D_x^2 + E_f \eta D_x^2,$$

$$k_{12} = \frac{\mu + \lambda}{12\lambda_2} \bar{\Delta}_y \bar{\Delta}_z^2 D_x, \quad k_{13} = \frac{\mu + \lambda}{12\lambda_3} \bar{\Delta}_z \bar{\Delta}_y^2 D_x,$$

$$k_{22} = \frac{\mu}{36} \bar{\Delta}_y^2 \bar{\Delta}_z^2 D_x^2 + \frac{2\mu + \lambda}{6\lambda_2^2} \bar{\Delta}_y \bar{\Delta}_z^2 D_x^2$$

Fig.1 Fiber Reinforced Rectangular Bar

Fig.2 Finite Prism Element

$$+ \frac{\mu}{6\lambda_3^2} \Delta_z^2 \Delta_y^2 + \mu_f \kappa_f \eta D_x^2, \quad k_{23} = \frac{\mu + \lambda}{4\lambda_2 \lambda_3} \Delta_y \Delta_z, \quad k_{24} = k_{25} = \mu_f \kappa_f \eta D_x,$$

$$k_{33} = \frac{\mu}{36} \Delta_y^2 \Delta_z^2 D_x^2 + \frac{2\mu + \lambda}{6\lambda_3^2} \Delta_z^2 \Delta_y^2 + \frac{\mu}{6\lambda_2^2} \Delta_z^2 \Delta_y^2 + \mu_f \kappa_f \eta D_x^2,$$

$k_{44} = k_{55} = \mu_f \kappa_f - D_x^2 E_f r_f^2$, and remaining elements are zero.

$$\{U\}^T = \{u, v, w, -\theta^y, -\theta^z\}, \quad D_x = d/dx, \quad \bar{\Delta}^2 = \Delta^2 + 6, \quad \eta = A_f/A_p, \quad A_p = \lambda_2 \lambda_3,$$

$$\Delta^2 f(y) = f(y+1) - 2f(y) + f(y-1), \quad \Delta f(y) = f(y+1) - f(y-1).$$

μ , λ denote Lamé's elastic constants and ρ density of the matrix matter.

[M] is a diagonal matrix in which

$$m_{11} = m_{22} = m_{33} = \frac{\rho}{36} \Delta_y^2 \Delta_z^2 + \rho_f \eta, \quad m_{44} = m_{55} = \rho_f r_f^2$$

and E_f , μ_f , r_f , A_f , κ_f and ρ_f are elastic modulus, elastic shear modulus, radius of gyration, sectional area, shear coefficient and density of fiber, respectively.

In case of plane wave with respect to the y and z coordinates, the Eq.(2) turns out the following forms

$$(C_{11} + E_f \eta) D_x^2 u = \rho^* u'' \quad (3)$$

$$(C_{44} + \mu_f \kappa_f \eta) D_x^2 v - \mu_f \kappa_f \eta D_x \theta^y = \rho^* v'' \quad (4)$$

$$(C_{44} + \mu_f \kappa_f \eta) D_x^2 w - \mu_f \kappa_f \eta D_x \theta^z = \rho^* w'' \quad (5)$$

where $C_{11} = 2\mu + \lambda$, $C_{44} = \mu + \eta \mu_f$, $\rho^* = \rho + \eta \rho_f$, $' = d/dt$

, which coincide with the equations of Achenbach et al(4).

The harmonic wave propagating in the x direction may be written in the following expressions

$$u = U \cos \frac{2\pi}{\ell}(x-ct), \quad v = V \sin \frac{2\pi}{\ell}(x-ct), \quad w = W \sin \frac{2\pi}{\ell}(x-ct), \quad (6)$$

$$\theta^y = \Theta^y \cos \frac{2\pi}{\ell}(x-ct), \quad \theta^z = \Theta^z \cos \frac{2\pi}{\ell}(x-ct)$$

where c , ℓ , Θ^y , Θ^z are phase velocity, wave length and slopes produced by the rotation of the fiber with respect to z and y axes, respectively.

Substitution of Eq.(6) in Eq.(2) yields the finite difference equations, which is easily treated by means of "Finite Integration Transforms(7)".

Considering the symmetry and antisymmetry of the wave modes and applying the following boundary conditions;

$$\sigma_z = \tau_{xz} = \tau_{yz} = 0 \quad ; \text{ at top and bottom surfaces, and}$$

$$\sigma_y = \tau_{yz} = \tau_{xy} = 0 \quad ; \text{ at right and left side surfaces,}$$

we finally find the eigenvalue matrix from which we can calculate the phase velocity of the wave by iteration method.

Table 1 Longitudinal Wave

r_0^*	Fraser	Nigro	Tanaka second	author		
				48 div.	24 div.	8 div.
0.1	1.6120	1.6120	—	1.6112	1.6120	1.6150
0.3	1.6080	1.6080	—	1.6086	1.6092	1.6125
0.5	1.5996	1.5996	1.5997	1.6003	1.6010	1.6044
1.0	1.5512	1.5511	1.5511	1.5519	1.5526	1.5564
1.2	1.5150	—	1.5149	1.5155	1.5163	1.5208
1.4	1.4657	—	1.4656	1.4661	1.4668	1.4724
1.6	1.4048	—	—	1.4049	1.4055	—
1.8	1.3385	—	1.3384	1.3382	1.3387	1.3464
2.0	1.2743	1.274	1.2743	1.2738	1.2740	1.2823
2.2	1.2172	—	1.2172	1.2164	1.2165	1.2250
2.4	1.1687	—	1.1687	1.1677	1.1677	1.1763
2.6	1.1285	—	1.1285	1.1275	1.1274	1.1360
2.8	1.0956	—	1.0956	1.0945	1.0944	1.1032
3.0	1.0688	1.069	1.0688	1.0676	1.0675	1.0766
3.2	—	—	1.0469	1.0457	1.0457	1.0551
3.4	1.029	—	1.0296	1.0278	1.0279	1.0378
3.6	—	—	1.0143	1.0132	1.0133	1.0238
3.8	—	—	1.0022	1.0011	1.0014	1.0124
4.0	0.992	0.992	0.9922	0.9912	0.9915	1.0032
5.0	0.962	0.962	0.9619	0.9613	0.9623	0.9776
6.0	0.948	0.948	0.9487	0.9482	0.9502	0.9691
7.0	0.942	0.942	0.9418	0.9419	0.9448	—
8.0	0.938	0.939	0.9381	0.9387	0.9426	—
9.0	0.936	0.937	0.9359	0.9371	0.9420	—
10.0	0.934	0.936	0.9345	0.9362	0.9423	—
12.0	0.932	0.937	0.9327	0.9354	0.9441	—
14.0	0.931	0.939	0.9316	0.9366	0.9467	—
16.0	0.931	0.942	—	0.9366	0.9497	—

Table 2 First Screw Wave

r_0^*	Fraser	Nigro	Tanaka third	author		
				48 div.	24 div.	8 div.
0.1	—	—	22.2909	22.225	22.271	—
0.3	—	—	7.3985	7.379	7.3977	7.5735
0.5	—	—	4.4057	4.457	4.4043	4.5988
1.0	2.1646	2.165	2.1656	2.1653	2.1683	2.2181
1.2	1.8074	—	—	1.8119	1.8104	1.8425
1.4	1.5640	—	1.5640	1.5646	1.5664	1.5881
1.6	1.3926	—	1.3929	1.3931	1.3944	1.4088
1.8	1.2694	—	1.2694	1.2697	1.2707	1.2795
2.0	1.1793	1.1793	1.1794	1.1795	1.1802	1.1846
2.2	1.1127	—	1.1129	1.1129	1.1133	1.1141
2.4	1.0631	—	1.0635	1.0632	1.0633	1.0613
2.6	1.0258	—	1.0262	1.0258	1.0257	1.0215
2.8	—	—	0.9980	0.9975	0.9971	0.9912
3.0	0.9757	0.9761	0.9766	0.9759	0.9753	0.9682
3.2	0.9594	—	0.9602	0.9593	0.9586	0.9505
3.4	0.9467	—	0.9476	0.9467	0.9456	0.9370
3.6	0.9368	—	0.9378	0.9367	0.9356	0.9267
3.8	0.9292	—	0.9303	0.9290	0.9278	0.9187
4.0	0.9232	0.9236	0.9244	0.9230	0.9216	0.9127
5.0	0.908	0.9090	0.9097	0.9076	0.9056	0.8996
6.0	0.904	0.9056	0.9059	0.9032	0.9002	0.8997
7.0	0.903	0.9058	0.9055	0.9019	0.8981	0.9045
8.0	0.903	0.9074	0.9061	0.9016	0.8968	0.9110
9.0	0.903	0.9096	0.9071	0.9014	0.8958	0.9178
10.0	0.903	0.9121	0.9080	0.9010	0.8949	0.9246
12.0	—	0.9176	0.9096	0.9002	0.8939	—
14.0	—	0.9234	0.9110	0.9000	0.8943	—
16.0	—	0.9294	0.9121	0.8976	0.8961	—

Table 3 Torsional Wave

r_0^*	Fraser	Nigro	Tanaka	author		
				48 div.	24 div.	8 div.
0.1	—	0.9185	—	0.9181	0.9165	0.8967
0.5	0.9183	0.9182	0.9294	0.9180	0.9164	0.8965
1.0	0.9182	0.9178	0.9211	0.9177	0.9161	0.8961
2.0	0.9169	0.9162	0.9182	0.9165	0.9147	0.8948
3.0	—	0.9134	0.9162	0.9147	0.9125	0.8937
4.0	0.9130	0.9096	0.9143	0.9126	0.9097	0.8937
5.0	—	0.9054	0.9124	0.9110	0.9066	0.8958
10.0	0.9050	0.9018	0.9081	0.9024	0.8955	0.9251
12.0	0.9050	0.9095	0.9082	0.9007	0.8941	0.9371
14.0	0.9050	0.9185	0.9087	0.8991	0.8944	0.9422

Table 4 Second Screw Wave

r_0^*	Fraser	Nigro	Tanaka	author		
				48 div.	24 div.	8 div.
0.1	—	—	19.6374	22.1000	21.6650	—
0.5	3.8400	3.8430	3.8413	3.8600	3.8828	4.0263
1.0	1.9680	1.9690	1.9684	1.9696	1.9725	1.9991
2.0	1.2246	1.2250	1.2248	1.2225	1.2214	1.2255
3.0	1.0677	1.0680	1.0680	1.0658	1.0648	1.0688
4.0	—	1.0150	1.0148	1.0129	1.0123	1.0191
5.0	0.9900	0.9900	0.9905	0.9889	0.9890	0.9992
10.0	0.9520	0.9530	0.9526	0.9520	0.9580	0.9847
12.0	0.9460	0.9520	0.9469	0.9484	0.9559	0.9862
14.0	0.942	0.9520	0.9429	0.9459	0.9558	0.9880

Table 5 Flexural Wave

r_0^*	Fraser	Nigro	Timoshenko	Tanaka	author		
					48 div	24 div	8 div
0.1	0.0925	0.0925	0.1376	—	0.0921	0.0921	0.0900
0.3	0.2643	0.2642	0.2236	—	0.2640	0.2639	0.2640
0.5	0.4058	0.4058	0.4048	—	0.4056	0.4055	0.4056
1.0	0.6316	0.6316	0.6279	0.6316	0.6313	0.6313	0.6325
2.0	0.8081	0.8081	0.7400	0.8083	0.8080	0.8082	0.8122
3.0	0.8664	0.8666	0.8008	0.8668	0.8664	0.8671	0.8747
4.0	0.8893	0.8902	0.8365	0.8901	0.8897	0.8909	0.9032
5.0	0.8990	0.9008	0.8589	0.9000	0.8994	0.9016	0.9194
6.0	0.9020	0.9063	0.8738	0.9043	0.9035	0.9067	0.9303
7.0	0.9030	0.9098	0.8840	—	0.9053	0.9098	0.9387
8.0	0.9030	0.9128	0.8914	—	0.9063	0.9121	0.9456
10.0	—	0.9181	0.9042	—	0.9077	0.9164	0.9567
14.0	—	0.9285	0.9117	—	0.9108	0.9253	0.9715

DISCUSSION OF ACCURACY

In order to check the accuracy with the number of prism element, the nondimensional wave velocity c/c_s in the homogeneous isotropic square bar is taken into account, where c_s is shear wave velocity of the matrix.

The results calculated by Fraser(1), Nigro(2), Tanaka et al.(3) and the presenting method are tabulated in Table 1, 3 and 5 for longitudinal wave, torsional wave and flexural wave, respectively.

Incidentally the longitudinal and torsional wave tribute the first and second screw wave, respectively, in case of the square section because the symmetry about the diagonal can exist. It is also seen in the Table 2 and 4.

In the tables we can see the values of the presenting method gradually tend to the results of Nigro as γb^* increases, in which γb^* denotes $2\pi b^*/\lambda$.

Fig.3 Effects of P_f/ρ

Fig.4 Effects of E_f/E

Fig.6 Group Velocity

Fig.5 Effects of aspect ratio b/a

LONGITUDINAL WAVE

Effects of the density ratio ρ_f/ρ and the elastic modulus ratio E_f/E between fiber and matrix on the phase velocity of the fiber reinforced square bar are shown in Fig. 3 and 4 by the variations of nondimensional phase velocity c/c_s with nondimensional wave number γb^* for $\nu = 0.25$ and $\kappa_f = 0.886$. In this case, 8×8 square prism elements are taken.

Seeing the values c/c_s for $\gamma b^* = 0.1$ in Fig.3, c/c_s become smaller in sequence of $\rho_f/\rho = 1.0, 3.0, 5.0$ and 10.0 .

And in Fig.4 we can see the velocity gain due to the fiber, against the velocity in the case of without the fiber.

The nondimensional phase velocity c/c_s of the rectangular bar with and without the reinforcement for the three cases of aspect ratio $b/a = 1.0, 1.2$ and 2.0 , are shown in Fig.5 by the full line and the broken line, respectively, besides them, the results by means of " Effective Elastic Constants(\bar{E}) " are drawn by the chain line.

The figures show the effective modulus theory gives larger value than the finite prism method for γb^* larger than 1.

The group velocity c_g is related with the phase velocity c with

$$c_g = c + m \frac{dc}{dm} \tag{7}$$

where m is wave number, by which c/c_s derived from the phase velocity curves for $\nu = 0.25, E_f/E = 10$ and $\rho_f/\rho = 3$, c_g can be found as shown in Fig.6.

TORSIONAL WAVE

Effects of the elastic modulus ratio between fiber and matrix E_f/E on the phase velocity of the fiber reinforced square bar are shown in Fig.7 for the four cases of $E_f/E = 5, 10, 20$ and 100 .

In the numerical calculation, 8×8 square prism elements are also taken, and $\rho_f/\rho = 3.0, \eta = 0.1$ and $\nu = 0.25$.

The equivalent elastic modulus of torsion(\bar{G}) for the fiber reinforced rectangular bar is numerically compared with the finite prism method in Fig.8

Fig.7 Effects of E_f/E

Fig. 9 Group Velocity

Fig. 8 Effects of b/a

for the four cases of $b/a = 1.0, 1.2, 1.6$ and 2.0 where $E_f/E = 10$, $\rho_f/\rho = 3.0$ and $\nu = 0.25$.

The figure shows the E.M.T. gives larger value than the finite prism method for γb^* larger than 1.

The group velocity c_g obtained by Eq.(7) is also shown in Fig.9.

FLEXURAL WAVE

Effects of the aspect ratio b/a of the rectangular bar with and without the reinforcement, on the flexural wave velocity are shown in Fig. 10 for the three cases of $b/a = 1.0, 1.2$ and 2.0 . In every case, $E_f/E = 10$, $\rho_f/\rho = 3$ and $\nu = 0.25$.

c/c_s becomes larger in sequence of $b/a = 1.0, 1.2$ and 2.0 for γb^* less than 4.

The effective elastic modulus theory is also numerically compared with the F.P.M. in Fig.11 where $E_f/E = 10$, $\rho_f/\rho = 3$ and $\nu = 0.25$.

The figure shows the E.M.T. gives smaller value than F.P.M. around 4 of γb^* and a little larger value as γb^* increases.

Fig.12 shows the group velocity c_g obtained by Eq.(7).

Fig.10 Effects of b/a

CONCLUSION

Summarizing the above, we have come to the conclusions as follows;

- 1) Comparison of the presenting numerical results with those by others, claims that the presenting method is quite near the Nigro's one when the number of prism element is sufficient.
- 2) The effects of the fiber reinforcement on the longitudinal and torsional wave velocity of the composite rectangular bar is the larger gain with the higher rise of the fiber rigidity.

Fig.12 Group Velocity

Fig.11 Comparison with E.M.T.

Fig.5 and Fig.8 seem to show that the larger aspect ratio becomes, the smaller phase velocity takes place.

- 3) The effective modulus theory gives larger value than finite prism method of γb^* larger than 1 in the figures of longitudinal and torsional waves.
- 4) The figure of flexural wave shows the effective modulus theory gives smaller value than finite prism method around $\frac{1}{4}$ of γb^* and a little larger value more than $\frac{1}{4}$.

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